

VETERINARY SURVEILLANCE DOCTORS FROM THE UKRAINIAN AND BELARUSIAN KATYN LISTS INCLUDED IN THE LIST OF THOSE MURDERED IN THE KATYN MASSACRE

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The Katyn Massacre is the term used to describe the act of genocide committed in the spring of 1940 by NKVD officers against Polish prisoners of war held in Soviet special camps and in prisons in Western Belarus and Western Ukraine. Given this definition of the Katyn Massacre, and in accordance with the decision of the Politburo of the Central Committee of the All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks) of March 5, 1940, I have decided to include in this publication, alongside the 110 veterinarians murdered in Katyn and Kharkiv, another 10 doctors who were murdered in prisons in Western Belarus and Western Ukraine. Therefore, 120 veterinarians died in the Katyn Massacre.

Because the dates of death of veterinarians imprisoned under Soviet occupation are difficult to determine, and because the available data are uncertain and incomplete, I initially intended to keep these individuals on a separate list until the doubts were resolved. After further consideration and a review of the literature on the subject, however, I concluded that no exceptions should be made and that those doctors whose deaths are documented should be added to the list of those murdered in the Katyn massacre pursuant to the decision of the highest authorities of the USSR contained in the secret resolution of the Politburo of the Central Committee of the All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks) of March 5, 1940 (the so-called "Katyn Decision"). The so-called "Ukrainian and Belarusian Katyn Lists" are terms closely related to the Katyn massacre. The NKVD murdered approximately 21,800 prisoners of war pursuant to the aforementioned Politburo decision. The crimes were committed in the Katyn Forest (approx. 4,400 victims), Kharkiv (approx. 3,800), Kalinin (approx. 6,300), and in NKVD prisons in western Ukraine (the "Ukrainian Katyn List", approx. 3,425), where prisoners were murdered in NKVD prisons in Kyiv, Kharkiv, and Kherson and buried in Pyatykhatky near Kharkiv, in Bykivnia near Kyiv, and probably also in Kharkiv and Kherson. They were also committed in prisons in western Belarus (the "Belarusian Katyn List", approx. 3,870), where prisoners were murdered in Minsk and probably buried in Kuropaty.

UKRAINIAN KATYN LIST

The term "Ukrainian Katyn List" has been used to describe a list of 3,435 Poles arrested in Ukraine in 1940 by the NKVD and subsequently never heard from again. The Ukrainian Katyn List, together with its files, was sent on November 25, 1940, from the 1st Special Department of the NKVD of the Ukrainian SSR to the head of the 1st Special Department of the NKVD of the Soviet Union. After 54 years, on May 5, 1994, the Ukrainian Katyn List was handed over to the authorities of the Republic of Poland. However, it is not a complete list. Research has led to the conclusion that the NKVD in Ukraine murdered 4,181 Poles. Polish officers were murdered at NKVD headquarters in Kyiv and buried in mass graves in Bykivnia. In Ukraine, Poles were also murdered in other prisons, including those in Kharkiv and Kherson.

The list includes the following names: Jan Antoni Białoskórski – local government veterinarian in Łokacze, Horochów County; Włodzimierz Bilecki – local government veterinarian in Cieszanów; Kazimierz Deszberg – head of the veterinary service of District VIII Corps, holding the rank of lieutenant colonel; Zdzisław Zygmunt Karpiński – director of the municipal slaughterhouse in Lviv; Jan Mrzygłodzki – major of the Polish Army, professional officer; and Ludwik Bilewicz – regional council veterinarian. "Doctor, for some time now I have been planning to write about the biographies of several veterinarians. The time has finally come to do so," Dr. W. L. wrote to the author. "In your book 'Veterinarians Victims of World War II', you included information about Zdzisław Karpiński, among others, on the basis of Konrad Millak [1]. The information provided by that author is incorrect, as I had the opportunity to verify after a lecture I gave several years ago about veterinary surgeons and Knights of the Virtuti Militarii. I received a book written by Major Karpiński's son in which he describes the fate of his family from the moment of his arrest and deportation. The Major is listed on the so-called Ukrainian List, No. 1237. For the sake of completeness, I quote the biography from the aforementioned book [2]."

ZDZISŁAW ZYGMUNT KARPIŃSKI

He was born on February 14, 1890, in Leżachów, Jarosław County, the son of Michał and Joanna, née Waligórska. He received his veterinary diploma in Lviv in 1920. He served in the Polish Legions, receiving the Cross of Valor four times, and was transferred to the reserve in 1923 with the rank of major. He defended his doctoral thesis entitled "A Contribution to the Treatment of Esophageal Incision in Cattle" and obtained the degree of Doctor of Science. In 1934, he was a municipal veterinarian in Jarosław and held the rank of major in the Polish Army. In 1935, he was appointed director of the municipal slaughterhouse in Lviv. He lived in Lviv. He died with his family in 1939 in Lviv, murdered by the Gestapo. The "Index of the Repressed" of the KARTA Center contains information about Zdzisław Zygmunt Karpiński, born in 1890 and deceased in 1940 in Ukraine. The data come from the "Ukrainian List", a list of Polish citizens murdered in

Ukraine pursuant to the decision of the Politburo of the All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks) and the highest state authorities of the USSR of March 5, 1940 (copy No. IV/W186-/39/1237[55/4]). The "Katyn Cemeteries" website lists the Bykivnia cemetery. After the first edition of *Niepowtarzalni* was published, I received the following information from Ms. Aleksandra Roszkowska from Puławy (Dr. Z. Karpiński's family): "After his arrest by the NKVD in January 1940, he disappeared without a trace. His wife, Anna, and his three sons were exiled to the East. His eldest son, Jerzy, died in the USSR, while his wife and sons, Wiesław and Janusz, eventually settled in Canada after wartime exile. Zdzisław Karpiński was still being sought by the Polish Red Cross and KARTA, but unfortunately the place of his death has not yet been determined."

Translation of the epilogue by Dr. Wojciech Lietz from the book by Dr. Zdzisław Karpiński's sons, Janusz and Wiesław: "For 54 years after his arrest, we had no news of our father. Only in 1994 did an organization collecting information on the Katyn massacre receive a list of 3,435 prisoners. This was a new, previously unknown list, sent to Moscow by the head of the NKVD in Ukraine. The list is dated November 25, 1940, and is likely a list of prisoners deported for execution. My father's name (Zdzisław Karpiński) appears as number 1237 on this list, together with his date of birth and his father's name. Unfortunately, we have no other information about my father's fate, but we are convinced that he was murdered."

My brother Vic was a pilot in the Polish Armed Forces in England and flew Lancaster bombers over Berlin. After the war, he married a Polish woman living in Winnipeg and emigrated to Canada, where he took up farming. My mother, like us, made it to Iran and then to Rhodesia, where she found work. In 1949, she moved to Canada to join her son. There she worked in a hospital in Toronto. After retiring, she spent some time in Mexico studying Spanish. She died in 1969 at the age of 75. I finished school in Glasgow and then attended various courses at universities in England and Scotland. In 1949, I moved to Canada and joined my mother and brother. In 1950, I married an English woman, to whom I am still married. We have two children and four grandchildren. I am currently enjoying a well-deserved retirement. I wrote this book in the belief that it will help our children and grandchildren better understand their Polish roots.

One additional noteworthy detail is that Zdzisław Karpiński was one of four veterinarians awarded the *Virtuti Militari*, Class V, for the 1920 war, according to written information from Dr. W. Lietz of Gliwice.

JAN ANTONI BIAŁOSKÓRSKI

He was born in 1905. He received his veterinary diploma in 1931 from the Academy of Veterinary Medicine in Lviv and worked as a local government veterinarian. In 1939, he lived in Łokacze, Horochów County. In the list of veterinarians required to register,

prepared after World War II, he is listed under item 46 as one who failed to do so. This indicates that he either did not return to Poland or was killed. The Ukrainian Katyn List includes the name Jan Białoskórski, as I wrote in my book *For the Freedom of Poland*, vol. 2. I have not been able to confirm this today. However, the list does include Jan Białoskórski, born in 1886. The State Archives hold a file containing a judgment of the Warsaw District Court declaring Jan Białoskórski dead in 1949, after his disappearance sometime between 1939 and 1945.

WŁODZIMIERZ BILECKI

He was born in 1895 and was of Russian nationality. He obtained his veterinary diploma in 1926 from the Academy of Veterinary Medicine in Lviv. After the end of World War II, he did not comply with the mandatory registration requirement. The Ukrainian Katyn List includes a Włodzimierz Bilecki, born in 1900, son of Theodosius. The tragic event in question probably does not concern W. Bilecki, the veterinarian.

KAZIMIERZ DESZBERG

Born on July 17, 1875, he was the son of Jan and Eufrozyna. He obtained his veterinary degree from the Academy of Veterinary Medicine in Lviv in 1899. After graduation, he worked as an assistant. He later worked in Pilzno, Ternopil, and Zbarazh. In 1922, he defended his doctoral dissertation and obtained the degree of Doctor of Veterinary Medicine. He was married to Stanisława, née Korostenska. They had two sons: Jerzy, born in 1909, and Jerzy, born in 1928. Initially, he served in the Austrian army as a career officer. Later, in the Polish Army, he served as head of the veterinary service of District VIII Corps in the Toruń garrison, holding the rank of lieutenant colonel. He retired in 1939 and lived in Lviv. Prof. Wł. Lutyński, in his "List of Veterinary Doctors Who Were Prisoners of Camps...", adds that, owing to the absence of source N (the NKVD deportation list), he may have been murdered outside Kharkiv.

The "KARTA Center Index of the Repressed" states: Kazimierz Deszberg, son of Jan, born in 1875, died in 1940 in Ukraine (reference number IV/W 186-/17/862[55/5]). The "Katyn Cemeteries" website lists the Bykivnia cemetery. According to the "Katyn List and the Ukrainian Katyn List," Colonel Kazimierz Deszberg is listed on the so-called Ukrainian Katyn List as number 862 – he was murdered in 1940.

Prof. J. Tropiło [3] provides a different surname: Deszeberg K. s. Jana – this is likely a typographical error. Dr. Kazimierz Deszberg's son, Jerzy, born on June 1, 1909, was captured by the Soviets and murdered in Katyn in 1940.

JAN MRZYGLÓDZKI/MRZEGODZKI/MRZYGOCKI

He was born in 1891. He obtained his veterinary diploma in 1915 from a university in Vienna. In the 1931 census, he was listed as a major in the Polish Army and a professional officer. In the similar 1939 census, his "professional occupation" was given as state physician and his place of residence as Toruń. Colonel Konrad Millak [4] wrote in his biography: "He was born in 1891 in Lesser Poland and received his veterinary diploma in 1915 in Vienna. He participated in the First World War as a veterinarian in the Austrian army and then served in the Polish Army with the rank of lieutenant-major veterinarian (1918-1939)." He is listed under item 558 in the List of Veterinarians Who Did Not Submit to Mandatory Registration After World War II. IPN file on the Index of the Repressed page: Jan Mrzygocki, son of Andrzej, born 1891, arrested in the Lviv Voivodeship in 1940. The List of those murdered in Lviv prisons in June 1941 includes Jan Mrzegodzki, born 1891, son of Andrzej, and shot in Prison No. 1 in Lviv on June 26, 1941 – item 1080.

LUDWIK BILEWICZ

Born in 1897, he was the son of Marian. He obtained his veterinary diploma from the Academy of Veterinary Medicine in Lviv in 1927. He worked in Bielsk County as a regional veterinarian in Narew and also in Tarnogród, Biłgoraj County. He was arrested on May 23, 1940. The sentence was carried out on October 11, 1940. He died in Lviv in the "Brygidki" prison on Kazimierzowska Street. Confirmation of this tragedy can be found in the fact that Dr. L. Bilewicz did not appear in the mandatory post-war registration list.

The website indeksrepresjonowanych contains a file concerning Ludwik Bilewicz, son of Marian, born in 1897, which refers to a sentence carried out on October 11, 1940, namely exile to the Ukhtizhlag labor camp. Therefore, this veterinarian cannot be counted among those murdered in the Katyn massacre. Those murdered by the Soviets, with the participation of Ukrainians, in Lviv prisons in June 1941, while fleeing the advancing Wehrmacht, should be added to the Ukrainian Katyn List. Tadeusz Dzendzel, Tadeusz Kroczek, and Tadeusz Sęk were murdered in Lviv prisons at that time.

At the Institute of National Remembrance, I came across a list of those murdered in Lviv prisons in June 1941. After checking more than 1,800 names, it may seem that the names listed in the title correspond to veterinarians who failed to submit to mandatory registration after World War II. Why do I write "it seems" in a work that aspires to academic standards? This caution stems from the fact that in only one case do the personal data fully match those on the aforementioned list; in the remaining cases, there are discrepancies. For example, the missing veterinarian Jan Mrzygłodzki appears on the list of those murdered as Jan Mrzegodzki, and Tadeusz Dzendzel appears as Tadeusz Dzendel.

At the beginning of the German-Soviet war in 1941, the staff of the "Brygidki" prison on Kazimierzowska Street in Lviv (Prison No. 4) simply fled in fear of the Germans.

On express orders from Moscow, Beria returned to complete the massacre of the imprisoned political prisoners. Machine guns were used, and prisoners were murdered in their cells either by single shots or by grenades thrown inside. The massacre lasted two days, June 25 and 26, 1941. Between 3,500 and 7,000 prisoners were murdered in Lviv's prisons: Prison No. 1 on Łąckiego Street, Prison No. 2 on Zamarstynowska Street (Zamarstynów), and Prison No. 4 on Kazimierzowska Street.

Veterinarians were likely among the murdered.

TADEUSZ MIKOŁAJ DZENDZEL

He was born on February 12, 1901, in Przemyśl. He obtained his veterinary diploma from the Academy of Veterinary Medicine in Lviv in 1934. He worked in the Tarnopol Voivodeship as a municipal veterinarian in Brody. Dr. S. Jakubowski [5] adds: "He died during the occupation." The biography presented above comes from the book *Veterinarians: Victims of World War II*. It can be supplemented by an excerpt from the aforementioned list, item 436: "Dzendel Tadeusz, son of Stanisław, born in 1901 — shot in prison on June 26, 1941."

TADEUSZ LESZEK SĘK

Born on March 12, 1889, he received his veterinary diploma from the Veterinary Academy in Lviv in 1921 (according to the "Alphabetical List of Physicians..." in 1922). In 1931, he was a district doctor in Kosów Pokucki. In 1939, he was a district veterinarian in Brody, Tarnopol Voivodeship. During the occupation, he was murdered in the "Brygidki" prison in Lviv, as described by S. Jakubowski.

The IPN files [6] contain a record stating that Tadeusz Sęk, son of Franciszka, born in 1889, was arrested in the Lviv Voivodeship in 1940. Another record states that he was imprisoned in Prison No. 1 in Lviv and shot there on June 26, 1941. The list of those arrested by the NKVD Directorate of the Lviv Region, who were held in Prison No. 1 of the Lviv Region in Lviv and shot in June 1941 in connection with the outbreak of hostilities, is based on data from the GBI of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, the archives of the Directorate of the Security Service of Ukraine of the Lviv Region, a copy from the Central Archives of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Administration (reference number U1/336/F), and the KARTA Center (reference number IV/W386B). The first biography above comes from the author's book *"Veterinarians, Victims of World War II"*, and the second from a later publication, *"History in Shades of Gray"*. Both biographies are confirmed by an entry found in the aforementioned List of Those Murdered in Lviv Prisons. Item 1364 contains the following entry: "Sęk Tadeusz, born in 1889, son of Franciszek. Executed in Prison No. 1 in Lviv on June 26, 1941."

TADEUSZ JULIAN KROCZAK (KROCZEK)

Figure 1. Tadeusz J. Kroczak (Kroczek). MW Archives at the Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences

He was born on August 23, 1913, in Lviv. He obtained his secondary school leaving certificate on May 21, 1931, from the King Stefan Batory State Gymnasium in Lviv. He served as a volunteer from 1936 to 1937 and as a deputy assistant at the Department of Microbiology and Hygiene of the Academy of Veterinary Medicine in Lviv from 1937 to 1939. He participated in the September 1939 campaign. "He died near Zhovkva"—this is a quotation from a biography prepared by Dr. Grzegorz Jakubik for the Second Dictionary. G. Jakubik cited S. Jakubowski's article "Losses of Polish Veterinary Science during World War II: Tadeusz Kroczek, assistant at the Academy of Veterinary Medicine in Lviv, participant in the September 1939 campaign. He died on the field of glory near Zhovkva." Unfortunately, this information could not be confirmed. I came across the surname Kroczek, but with a different first name—Tomasz, son of Marcin, born in 1915—on the List of People Murdered in Lviv Prisons, item 8252. He was executed in Prison No. 1 in Lviv on June 26, 1941. Further searches yielded no new information. The case probably does not concern the aforementioned veterinarian.

The two-day period in which prisoners were murdered in Lviv prisons was exceptionally tragic. Hence this brief description of those events, based on an excerpt from Krzysztof Szymański's article [7]: "71 years ago..." Maciej Rosalak recalls: "The whole world knows that exactly 70 years ago the Wehrmacht attacked the Red Army. Civilized humanity is also increasingly realizing that, in the hell unleashed in the East, the forces of Evil personified by Hitler did not attack an innocent Stalin, the defender of Good. A battle had begun between two bandits unlike any the world had ever seen, and between two insane political systems committing unprecedented crimes. It so happened that the latter,

willingly or unwillingly, while fighting for survival, became an ally of the democratic West. Yet few people still know the enormous blood toll paid by Poles at that time. Before fleeing from the Germans, the Soviets systematically and with monstrous brutality murdered political prisoners, most of whom were our compatriots. Anyone they did not shoot, tear apart with grenades, or wall up alive was driven east on death marches, starved, beaten, and killed. Even in the face of defeat, they did not forget to beat the 'class enemy'. Truly Bolshevik."

After a week of fighting, the Germans entered Lviv and quickly targeted the elite of the Polish intelligentsia—university professors who had managed to survive Soviet terror. After arrest, brief interrogation, and selection, several dozen were shot on Gestapo orders.

From this group, five veterinarians were included in the List of Those Murdered in the Katyn Massacre (their names are marked in bold in their biographies).

BELARUSIAN KATYN LIST

A few years ago, information surfaced about the discovery of the so-called "Belarusian Katyn List" in Russian archives. This information turned out to be false. The Belarusian Katyn List consists of disposition lists containing 3,870 people sentenced to death by the decision of March 5, 1940, and most probably murdered in 1940 in Minsk. The Center for Polish-Russian Dialogue and Understanding prepared a partially reconstructed "List of Polish citizens who may be included on the so-called Belarusian Katyn List" and provided it to the Russian side for review. Dr. Maciej Wyrwa compiled the names of approximately 1,149 missing persons from the northeastern voivodeships of the Second Polish Republic between September 17, 1939, and June 1940. This is an incomplete list of Polish citizens who were arrested or taken prisoner in 1939-1940 in the Białystok, Nowogródek, Vilnius, and Polesie voivodeships. "Since the fate of these people remains unknown, it can be assumed that some of them were murdered pursuant to the decision of the Politburo of the All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks) of March 5, 1940, and are listed on the so-called Belarusian Katyn List, which has not yet been found," as we read in the introduction to the aforementioned list.

The list contains several names that may refer to veterinarians, although in some cases the first name is missing or a different date of birth is given. These cases therefore require detailed clarification: Julian Puzyna—arrested at his estate in Polesie; Stanisław Jastrzębski—state veterinarian who in 1939 worked and lived in Vilnius; Eugeniusz Czekotowski—freelance veterinarian in Kcynia; Józef Gabriel Wysokiński—who in September 1939, with the rank of captain in the Polish Army, served on the staff of the 35th Infantry Division; and Włodzimierz Bocheński—freelance veterinarian in Widzibór in Polesie.

Item 762 of the reconstructed list reads: "Puzyna Julian, prince, arrested in Strychów (Stryhovo), Polesie Voivodeship, by the NKVD in September 1939, missing".

JULIAN PUZYNA

Born on May 27, 1890, he lived in Strychów, Kobryń County. He obtained his veterinary diploma in 1913. He was a full member of the Lutyko-Venedya Academic Fraternity in Lviv. Konrad Millak's memoirs, "Flowers for Anna", include the following description: "During the semester of my departure, two candidates arrived for Venedya: Roman Rulewicz and Julian Puzyna. I met them several times, even in September. I saw in them excellent, loyal material for Venedya. The value of the candidates lies in the future and longevity of the association. My predictions concerning the value of this last coitus recorded in my name were not disappointed."

Julian Puzyna, of the Oginiec coat of arms, married Róża Trębicka (1891-1983) of the Ślepowron coat of arms in 1920. K. Millak, in his article "Polish Veterinary Surgeons—Victims...", states that J. Puzyna was born in 1889 and received his diploma in Dorpat in 1915. He was a freelance veterinarian. However, the "Dictionary of Polish Veterinary Surgeons 1394-1918" provides a slightly different account: "Puzyna Julian, Prince of Kozielsk (1890-1939). Born in Kobryn, he received his veterinary diploma in 1915 in Dorpat. He participated in World War I as a veterinarian in the Russian army (1915-1918), and after the war served in the Polish Army (1918-1921) as a lieutenant-captain veterinarian. After leaving the army, he managed his estate in Strychów in the Kobryń district of the Polesie Voivodeship (1921-1939). He died in 1939."

According to Professor Wł. Lutyński, Julian Puzyna was arrested by the Soviets at his estate in Polesie after September 17, 1939, and then disappeared without a trace. The "List of Members of the Polish Academic Fraternity Lutyko-Venedya" (Lviv) states: "He died on the field of honor as a cavalry officer in September 1939." Meanwhile, Colonel Z. Łyjak wrote in his biography: "Capt. Veterinarian Julian Puzyna, a participant in the defensive war, disappeared during the fighting in September 1939."

Julian Puzyna was arrested on September 29, 1939, at his estate and imprisoned in Kobryń; this is where the record of his life ends.

Another name that may refer to a veterinarian appears under item 329: Stanisław Jastrzębski, who was arrested in Vilnius in October 1939 and imprisoned in Stara Wilejka prison, after which all trace of him disappeared.

STANISŁAW JASTRZĘBSKI

Figure 2. St. Jastrzębski – University of Warsaw Archives

He was born on October 10, 1907, in Będzin, the son of Antoni and Zofia, née Ziemska, and lived in the Ksawery settlement at 2 Paryska Street. He graduated from the Walerian Łukaszewicz State Gymnasium in Dąbrowa Górnicza, passing his final examinations on April 16, 1926. In the same year, on September 13, 1926, he applied for admission to the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Warsaw. After that application was rejected, he applied again, this time to the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, on October 12, 1926. This application was accepted, and Stanisław Jastrzębski began his studies in Warsaw. As a veterinary student, he repeatedly applied to the university authorities for a waiver of tuition fees because of his difficult financial situation. He attached to these applications a poverty certificate issued by the Żyrardów City Hall, Social Welfare Department, on October 13, 1927. He received veterinary diploma No. 158 on May 4, 1931. The 1939 "List of Veterinary Surgeons of the Republic of Poland" records that he was a state veterinarian residing in Vilnius. He is also listed in the post-war list of unregistered veterinarians.

At the outset, I stated that he had been imprisoned in Stara Vilejka. In 2004-2009, the Institute of National Remembrance conducted an investigation into the murders and abuse of prisoners in Prison No. 26 in Stara Vilejka, in the former Vilnius Voivodeship, committed by NKVD officers from September 1939 to June 1941 (S 137/04/Zk). The report on the discontinuation of this investigation states: "In the course of the proceedings initiated on November 30, 2004, statements were taken from 120 witnesses recognized as political prisoners who had been imprisoned in the prison in Stara Vilejka. Mass killings

took place during the evacuation of the prison after the outbreak of the Soviet-German war. On June 23, 1941, several dozen inmates were left in their cells, and a marching column was formed from approximately 1,400 prisoners. Because the railway lines had been bombed, the column was driven east on foot. Along the way, the guards murdered the wounded, the sick, and those who lagged behind or attempted to escape. Mass executions took place near the villages of Kasuty and Pleszczenice. After five days, the column reached Borysław, where the prisoners were loaded onto wagons and sent by rail to Ryazan. Upon arrival, 871 prisoners were counted. In the prison in Stara Vilejka, a group of men and women had been left behind. The men were shot by NKVD officers and their bodies were buried in the prison yard. Fleeing from the German troops, the guards set fire to the prison buildings. The executioners did not have time to murder the group of women, who were freed by the town's residents."

As a result of further research, I visited the Institute of National Remembrance, Branch of the Commission for the Prosecution of Crimes against the Polish Nation in Gdańsk, where prosecutor Maciej Schulz informed me that: "The documentation of the investigation, reference number S 137/04/Zk, into the murders committed by NKVD officers in Prison No. 26 in Vilejka does not include the name of Stanisław Jastrzębski, born October 10, 1907." A participant in those events recounts: "When the Soviets left Vileyka, we decided to enter the prison and freed the women. Some were unable to walk on their own, so we carried them out. They confirmed earlier reports that the Soviets had been shooting people in the prison. We found no traces or bodies of the victims either in the courtyard or inside the prison building. Only behind the prison wall, in a wooden shelter, was there a great deal of dried blood. We continued searching and came across a cage where trained dogs had been kept. One dog remained. When released, it led us straight to a freshly dug pit into which the prison sewage flowed. The dog began digging and unearthed a human hand. We took advantage of the 10 days of 'freedom' after the Red Army's departure. We exhumed 28 bodies and buried them in the cemetery, and the residents of the village of Kosuta informed us about 50 more bodies. Unfortunately, they could not be identified, and no documents were found on most of them. That was the first time in my life that I moved a human corpse..."

On the basis of these findings, we may tentatively assume that the arrest of veterinarian Stanisław Jastrzębski in October 1939 had a tragic end. Stanisław Jastrzębski was probably murdered during the evacuation of the prisoners, in which 529 of the 1,400 inmates were killed. The name of veterinarian Józef G. Wysokiński is also listed under item 912 of the List mentioned at the beginning.

JÓZEF GABRIEL WYSOKIŃSKI

He was born on March 26, 1905, in Zawady, Lublin Voivodeship, the son of Leopold and Apolonia Pniewska, and lived in Białystok. He passed his secondary school leaving

examination in 1924 at the Bolesław Prus State High School for Boys in Siedlce. He matriculated at the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Warsaw, on October 15, 1924. He received his veterinary diploma in 1930 (No. 1619) from the University of Warsaw. He was a captain veterinarian in the Polish Army at the Reserve Centre of the Suwałki and Podlasie Cavalry Brigade, 10th Lithuanian Uhlan Regiment. In September 1939, he served on the staff of the 35th Infantry Division. He disappeared in 1939.

I published Józef Wysokiński's biography in "Veterinarians Victims of World War II" and stated that he completed his veterinary studies in 1930 at the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Warsaw. In 1931, he was assigned to the Military Veterinary Laboratory as an assistant and, owing to seniority, was awarded the rank of second lieutenant among reserve officers called up for active service on January 1, 1931. He was promoted to the rank of captain on March 19, 1937, and mobilized into the 10th Lithuanian Uhlan Regiment. In 1934, at the University of Warsaw, he defended his doctoral thesis entitled "Bactericidal action of lactic acid on pyogenic microorganisms in vitro and its influence on disorders in purulent processes caused by these microorganisms."

Following T. Kryśka-Karski's "Losses of the Officer Corps 1939-1945", published in London in 1996, I stated that he died in 1940 in Starobielsk. It should be clarified, however, that the Soviets did not murder prisoners of war in the special camps of Starobielsk, Kozielsk, or Ostashkov. The inclusion of J. Wysokiński's name on the so-called Belarusian Katyn List is closer to the truth, indicating that he was murdered in a prison in western Belarus.

Stanisław Jastrzębski was deported from Mołodeczno to Minsk on June 12, 1940, by the 226th Regiment. In Minsk he was imprisoned, and all trace of him vanished. The Kresy Death List states that he died in Kuropaty.

While reviewing Dr. Maciej Wyrwa's list, I came across item 68, which contains the name of Włodzimierz Bocheński, who obtained his veterinary diploma in Kharkiv in 1902. This is the fourth victim among veterinary doctors on the reconstructed Belarusian Katyn List.

WŁODZIMIERZ BOCHEŃSKI

He was born on April 15, 1876, in Tersin, Kozangródek commune, Łuniniec district, Polesie Voivodeship. He obtained his veterinary diploma in Warsaw in 1902. Unfortunately, his student file is not held in the Archives of the University of Warsaw. K. Millak writes in the Dictionary: "He was assigned to the veterinary reserve of the Russian army (1903), was a district veterinarian in Olta, Kars Oblast, Caucasus (1908), and a local veterinarian in Łuniniec (1914); after World War I, he was a freelance veterinarian in Widzibór, Stolin district, Polesie (1921-1939). He died during the Nazi occupation."

He owned an estate in Widzibór. In April 1940, NKVD officers arrived there with an order to arrest the owner. From that moment onward he disappeared, and no trace of veterinarian Włodzimierz Bocheński has been found. He is another World War II victim from the veterinary community, joining the ranks of those murdered. Therefore, we cannot agree with the information presented above in Millak's Dictionary: "died during the Nazi occupation, 1941?"

W. Skowyra [8] reported that Włodzimierz Bocheński was first arrested in mid-September 1939 but released at the request of local residents. He was arrested a second time in April 1940. According to this account, he was murdered by the NKVD during the evacuation of a prison in Minsk on the night of June 23-24, 1941.

A more extensive biography can be found in the article by Żwanko [9], Kibkało D., and Sobolewski J.; the authors favor 1940 as the date of the crime.

Dr. M. Wyrwa does not (yet) mention the fifth doctor – Eugeniusz Czekotowski.

EUGENIUSZ CZEKOTOWSKI

Born on August 7, 1893, he was the son of Ludwik. He obtained his veterinary diploma in 1919 in Novochoerkassk. In his publication "Veterinary University in Warsaw", Colonel Konrad Millak also listed Eugeniusz Czekotowski among the staff of the Department of Surgery from 1925 onward. In 1927, he worked as a senior assistant in the Department and Clinic of Surgery of the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Warsaw. In 1934, he defended his doctoral thesis at the Academy of Veterinary Medicine in Lviv, entitled "Examination of meat from cattle for cysticercosis, taking into account histopathological examination." He later worked as a freelance veterinarian in Kcynia, Szubin County, and in Damasławek, Wągrowiec County.

The memorial plaque in Kcynia, listing those murdered in "other places of execution", reads: "(1893-1940), lieutenant, veterinarian in Kcynia and Damasławek." On the former monastery church of the Assumption of the Blessed Virgin Mary in Kcynia there is a commemorative plaque for those shot in the spring of 1940 by Stalin's NKVD; the plaque bears the inscription: "prisoners of Minsk: Eugeniusz Czekotowski – veterinarian." Meanwhile, the alphabetical "List of Polish Army Officers 1918-1921" records him as a second lieutenant, veterinary surgeon. The website of the Police in the Kuyavian-Pomeranian Voivodeship states that he was murdered by the NKVD in Minsk, in the "Amerykanka" prison, in April 1940. Dr. Eugeniusz Czekotowski was the author of several scientific papers: "A rare case of multiple pregnancy in a cow", *Wet. Wiad.* 1924, no. 48; "Procedure during a cholera outbreak in poultry", *Wet. Wiad.* 1924, no. 48; "Attempts at the practical application of peat in veterinary medicine", *Wet. Review* 1931, no. 4; "On the technique of examination for cysticercosis", *Wet. Review* 1932, no. 7;

"Periodic report from the public slaughterhouse in Chojny, Łódź district", *Vet. Review* 1933, no. 1; "Experimental studies on the condition of the surgical field when using chemical hair-removing agents", *Vet. Review* 1933, no. 6; and "A contribution to the examination of cattle meat for cysticercosis, taking into account histopathological examination", *Vet. Review* 1934, no. 8. This list of papers is based on K. Millak.

During research conducted in the Digital Archives of the Institute of National Remembrance, Poznań Branch, I located court records from proceedings for the declaration of death of Eugeniusz Czekotowski. The case was examined by the District Court in Wągrowiec, file reference IPN Po 452/14. The judgment concluded that he died in 1943 near Baranowicze.

Based on the information and documents available so far, we can confirm that the names of five veterinarians should have been included on the Belarusian Katyn List. Therefore, 120 veterinarians were murdered in the Katyn massacre.

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